

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

AI SYSTEM FOR PREDICTING NEONATAL PATIENT PROGNOSIS

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Abstract

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), Globally 2.3 million children died in the first 28 days of life in 2022. Some neonatal conditions can rapidly deteriorate and be fatal even without diagnosis. This research aimed to develop an AI-based diagnostic model for predicting the prognosis of neonatal patients using routine blood tests. The study involved live-born patients, including premature and full-term infants. To build the AI model, we used Matlab software. AI model for the prediction of neonatal patients' prognosis is determined by the high predictive accuracy (94%). The findings suggest that routine blood tests may provide more information that can help predict the prognosis of neonatal patients.

Keywords: Neonatal care, machine learning, prognosis prediction, disease diagnosis, intensive care, AI model for patient's prognosis.

Introduction: According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), Globally 2.3 million children died in the first 28 days of life in 2022. There are approximately 6500 newborn deaths every day, amounting to 47% of all child deaths under the age of 5 years. Newborns cannot communicate their symptoms, which makes early diagnosis of disease difficult. Many neonatal diseases may not be apparent at birth. Some neonatal conditions, such as sepsis, internal bleeding, or cardiovascular diseases, can rapidly deteriorate and be fatal even without diagnosis.

Various studies have shown that routine blood tests may contain additional information that is not available to the doctors and that an AI system may be able to uncover (*Simon Podnar at all. University Medical Center in Ljubljana*)

The goal of our research was to create an artificial intelligence-based model for predicting the prognosis of neonatal patients using the newborns routine blood tests.

Main part:

The study was retrospective, data was retrieved from the patient medical documentations In full compliance with the principles of medical ethics. Patients were treated in the neonatal intensive care unit of the Tbilisi Clinic "Pineo" Perinatal Center (2023-2024 year).

The medical documentations of 81 live-born patients were studied. Female 44, male 37, premature 60, full-term newborn 21, recovered 61, died 20. For creating AI model we used only the routine blood tests that were performed on all newborns within 8 hours of birth (Table 1).

Table. 1.

Routine tests used for the AI model.

Parameters for the AI Model			
Parameter	Units	Parameter	Units
WBC	$10^3 / \mu\text{L}$	RDW-CV	%
RBC	$10^6 / \mu\text{L}$	PLT	$10^3 / \mu\text{L}$
HGB	g/dl	MPV	fl
HCT	%	Neut	%
MCV	fl	LYMPH	%
MCH	pg	MONO	%
MCHC	g/dl	Eosino	%
ABO	--	Glucose	mmol/l
CRP	mg/l		

To build the AI model, we used a classification (Supervised machine learning method). As a software tool Matlab was used (Classification learner App). After pre-processing the data (routine blood tests results of 81 patients) machine learning model was build using 5 fold cross-validation and was trained using various statistical methods.

Results:

Various statistical methods were used to train the model (Linear SVM, Quadratic SVM, Cubic SVM, ALL SVMs, Coarse Gaussian, Fine Gaussian, medium Gaussian, Neural Network). The best results were obtained using Optimizable SVM, AI model for neonatal patient's prognosis is determined by the high predictive accuracy (94%). The model was exported and checked using the new data (figure 1).

Figure 1. True positive and False positive rates of the AI model.

Conclusion:

We have created AI powered predictive model for the predicting prognosis of neonatal patients based on blood routine tests. The model is characterized by high predictive accuracy (94%). The study is significant because it used only routine blood tests, conducted on all patients in the clinic, to develop the AI model. The findings suggest that these tests may provide more information that can help predict the prognosis of neonatal patients. This advancement will greatly aid clinicians in identifying at-risk groups and, through intensive monitoring, reduce complications and mortality rates.

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